

Women Social Entrepreneurs as Agents of Change: A Study of Rural Punjab

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Social entrepreneurial activities embedded for social purposes remain beneficial for the whole community. Such social entrepreneurial activities have been characterised and are more gender-focused, especially towards women. To understand the role of women in social entrepreneurial activities, this study was initiated in the Abhor district of Punjab. In a theoretical sense, the present study is based on a qualitative and narrative approach. The study is based on the life stories of four women who work as social change agents. Three case studies of farming women who started working in their farming fields, initiated their processing units and generated employment opportunities for the village women. The fourth case study is of a woman who established her pickle-making unit and gave employment opportunities to the village women to earn their livelihood. The study revealed that women shifted their realm from the private to the public sphere, boosting their confidence and increasing participation in the decision-making process. It also increased women's mobility and economic well-being, which caused their presence in society. The women become more active and expressive in a patriarchal household setup. However, women still face various challenges to increase their visibility in society and at the family level that need to be given consideration. This study will help policymakers and NGOs to curb gender discrimination and poverty-related problems using entrepreneurial activities.

Keywords: Social entrepreneur, women, agent of change, decision-making, gender, patriarchy

Our rural people may become more self-sufficient through the growth of entrepreneurs in agriculture and related fields, which will in turn help the economy grow (Aggarwal & Khare, 2019). As the constitution of India has given equal rights to both genders, women still face various challenges and do not share similar socio-economic freedom as men, especially in rural societies (Aggarwal et al., 2020). It is due to our social setup, in which society is based on patriarchal norms and women always remain subordinate to men. In such a system, males are confined to the head of the household and major decision-makers of the family (Kaur, 2022). While females always play a subordinate role and are confined to household tasks. Even the social set-up is also divided into the public and private spheres, in which women are restricted to the private sphere and men are confined to the public sphere (Debnath, 2015). In such a scenario, power dynamics play the biggest role and the male has become the breadwinner of the family, and also controls the economic means of the family (Chopra, 2011). In this way, women's role is confined to

rare and caring for children and household tasks. Women follow their male members in decision-making and work according to them (Kandiyoti, 1988). Moreover, women remain dependent on men for their economic needs because their household chores remain unrecognised by the family and society. This lack of recognition due to low participation in economic activities intensifies gender discrimination and gender disparity. Moreover, women's labour force participation in India is low and has been declining at an alarming rate, which portrays a negative outcome in women's and children's well-being (Rami, 2018). In India, the women's employment rate was 25% in 2018, which is a decline from 49% in 2004 (Krishna, 2022). In the rural areas, it is worse; women's LFP in rural areas fell from 26.5 per cent in 2009-10 to 18.2 per cent in 2017-18 (Jha, 2021). Hence, low work participation of women diminishes their economic status, decreases their role in family decision-making and loosens control over family resources (Krishnakumar & Viswanathan, 2021). No doubt, self-help groups, governmental and non-governmental organisations endeavour to provide them with education and also intervene through economic reliance for women to gainful employment opportunities (Kumar, 2013). However, such work still has limited outreach as women still face challenges in dealing with their household chores and breaking barriers of gender disparity (Kaur, 2022). So, in such cases, social entrepreneurial activities always play a wider role because rural women own certain skills and also have the abilities to use those skills for economic endeavours if supported actively (Aggarwal et al., 2021). In this context, social entrepreneurial activities embedded for social purposes remain beneficial for the whole community. Such social entrepreneurial activities have been characterised and are more gender-focused, especially towards women. To understand the role of women in social entrepreneurial activities, this study was initiated in Punjab. The present study discussed women as agents of change in

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their area and provided aid to other women for economic welfare. Before discussing case studies in detail, the next part of the paper will shed light on the existing literature, the third part will give a detailed explanation of data and methods, the fourth part of the paper will discuss case studies in a detailed manner and the last part is the conclusion.

Review of Literature

Social Entrepreneurship

Social entrepreneurship is a process of generating value by combining resources in new traditions. These resource arrangements are mainly planned to identify or seize the chances to embed social value by inspiring social transformation or addressing social needs. In addition to the process of contributing goods and services, social entrepreneurship can also refer to the process of starting new businesses. Social entrepreneurs can be identified by their highly distinctive traits, which include unique management abilities, a drive to realise their vision, and a strong ethical foundation. Mair and Marti (2006) identified three general categories of people who become social entrepreneurs are identified. The first group consists of people who have made a lot of money in other areas and are eager to donate some of it to support humanitarian causes. The second group consists of "recovering social workers," who are fed up with the current system of social support and seeking a more successful strategy. The third category is a brand-new breed that attended business schools (or followed a similar path) with a focus on social enterprise (Cannon, 2000). The poor and those at the bottom of the social pyramid would profit from a variety of social entrepreneurship-related aspects. It suggested innovations and social entrepreneurship leadership that would result in a total revolution of society (Brown, 2005). Women entrepreneurs have exceptional talents and skills, including leadership qualities, self-awareness, the ability to recognise opportunities, risk-taking prowess, and the capacity to commercialise resources by developing products and services to meet market demands. The development of entrepreneurial learning and abilities, which are essential for the success of female social entrepreneurs, has been seen to be impacted by personal, societal, and environmental factors (Agrawal, 2018). The ability to accept financial risk, the ability to reduce organisational risk, and the ability to be empowered as a social collective are the three main problems that women face. It also emphasises that there are various stages of business development, each requiring a unique strategy. Finally, if a social entrepreneurial sustainable model is implemented, it highlights a number of social, political, and economic benefits that are built into a social enterprise. Hockerts (2010) the degree of discrimination was either based on racial or ethnic background, or both, according to the data. This was attributed to a number of factors, such as stereotyped obstacles to receiving different types of formal social help, such as authorised financial and business support. The respondents' families were mentioned as a significant source of both emotional and practical assistance (Fielden & Davidson, 2012). Fourteen women from Northern Ireland participated in a qualitative study by McGowan et al. (2012) about how they built and ran their enterprises while juggling obligations to their families. The findings demonstrated that the reason for engaging in entrepreneurship was the desire to strike a balance between personal independence and family duties, thanks to the higher flexibility that is characteristic of this type of

job. The societal phenomenon of gender disparity has an impact on a variety of spheres of life, including the social, economic, legal, and institutional ones. It inhibits society from treating men and women equally. The socio-cultural disparities between male and female business activity are explained by variations in gendered linguistic patterns. Sociocultural factors are interwoven into various gendered roles and have an impact on company ownership rates (Terrell & Troilo, 2010).

Method

To understand the role of women in social entrepreneurial activities, this study was initiated in Abohar city of Punjab. This paper is the outcome of the researchers' (Kaur & Kaur, 2021) official training at RRS, Abohar. Dr Anil Kumar was initially in charge of the training. He is a horticulture expert. With his help, a pilot study was initiated in Abohar farming families. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the respondents and through an open-ended interview schedule, data were collected from four social entrepreneur women. In a theoretical sense, the present study is based on a qualitative and narrative approach. The study is based on the life stories of four women who work as social change agents. Three case studies of farming women who started working in their farming fields, initiated their processing units and generated employment opportunities for the village women. The fourth case study is of a woman who established her pickle-making unit and gave employment opportunities to the village women to earn their livelihood. The interviews were conducted with the permission of the respondents for ethical consideration. The interviews revolve around the role of women in entrepreneurial activities, gender dynamics, patriarchal family setup, mobility and decision-making.

Results

Case 1: Indu Jyani: Developing Eco-tourism and Processing Unit

Our first visit to Jyana Farm, which is known for Eco-tourism and Natural farming. This farm is spread over 130 acres of Land. During our visit, we met Indu Jyani. She was an entrepreneur and worked in Natural Farming. She has her own processing unit of Rose water and pluses. She has been working since 2005 in this area. She said that after the moisture in the area, the soil quality was affected, which had a bad impact on the Cotton belt. They faced a huge loss in their cotton farming and their spiritual guru directed them to natural farming. That was the main turning point in their life. They started natural farming. However, the main question is about how to start and where to start such kind of farming. So, Indu took initial training from the Central Institute of Post-Harvest Engineering and Technology and the Regional Research Station Abhor. So, they learned the technique to procure and grow natural farming. In 2005, her husband converted all the land into natural farming and without fertiliser. They tried to use cow dung-based manure in farming, which requires patience and hard work. So, after three years of hard work, they grow natural vegetables and sell them in the Kisan mela throughout India and Punjab. Before starting natural farming, Indu was a housewife and was taking care of her children. She did a Master's in Gandhian studies from Banasthali and also followed the model of Swadeshi. However, she never thought of working as an entrepreneur because of household responsibilities. It was her husband who motivated her to work with him. He said that women need to be independent if they

want to make changes in their society and she started full-time farming with her husband. Indu also fulfilled her mother's duty and invested her time to give a good education to her children. Her daughter was an IAS officer and her son completed a Master's degree in Agriculture from New Zealand. Now her son was also working in Natural Farming.

Indu mentioned that "her training in making rose water and pulse processing remained fruitful. She motivated her village women and gave them full-time employment opportunities on her farm. She started packing organic pulses for sale and all this work was handled by her women co-worker". They were making *Desi Ghee* from Sahiwal cows through the traditional method and started dairy farming also. For this work, she gave employment opportunities to village girls and also indulged her daughter-in-law. Her daughter-in-law was taking care of dairy farming.

She said that she wanted to pass her legacy to her son and daughter-in-law. I wanted them to take care of our farm and initiate natural farming more rigorously. Indu won the *Mehila Shakti Award 2020* for her exceptional achievement in the field of agriculture.

She mentioned that she wants her village women should be independent in economic matters. I want to create employment opportunities for them in agricultural farming so that they are not dependent on others. She already provided employment opportunities to 50 women and who were working in their orchid, vegetable cultivation, dairy farming and processing units. She also gave these women workers exposure to marketing during the Kisan Mela and other melas. She represents her team and also takes them to such melas to sell their products. Now she is working as a full-time entrepreneur. She has clients from family friends and the Kisan Mela. She wants her village girls to graduate from agriculture to become entrepreneurs. So that they can become self-sufficient and Independent.

Case 2. Renu Singhmar: Successful Farmer

The second success story is that we have Renu Singhmar, from Dharpur village, Abohar. She has 120 acres of land. She is working as a Farmer and cultivates Kinnow, Malta and seasonal crops. She started farming in 2015 after her husband's death. Before that, she was a housewife and was caring for her children. With the sudden demise of her husband with a heart attack. It has become a need of the hour. At that time, her children were school-going and she didn't have any idea about farming. Her husband and father-in-law were the main farmers. She felt her life at stake. She said that no doubt she was educated. She was a science graduate and also an interior designer in Delhi during her early years. She was an independent woman. Even after marriage, there was no restriction on her. But the turning point came after her husband's death. She became the earner of the family. So, to understand her family business, first, she met with her local labourers to learn about their land. She didn't even know about land. So, she got to know about her orchid and agricultural land. Then, she gave full-time attention to her farms. She started dairy farming also.

This time, she was handling her house and children. Her daughter was doing LLB and her son was in 10th class. She became head of the household and decision-maker of the family. She was making decisions related to her children's education. She wanted her daughter to be independent and also a working woman. While her son is in a young stage. She had 30 permanent labourers, whom she supervises. She made decisions related to agricultural land with the

help of labour. She appointed 20 women workers from her village as permanent and provided them with employment opportunities. These women were mainly working in orchids, vegetable cultivation and dairy farming.

She said, "Women of the village needed to be part of economic activities because most of the time these women remained busy in household activities and dependent upon their male members. I tried to make changes in their economic life so that they could become independent in their life. All, I realised after becoming a farmer and economic decision-maker of the household. Though choices and opportunities were different in all cases. These women needed someone who would help them grow independently. However, in my case, it was a family necessity. It boosted my confidence as well as my workers.

Recently, she was cultivating 79 acres of land on the orchid farm in which she planted Kinnow, pear, plum and Malta. She started marketing with the help of her brother and started selling her production to processing units. Earlier, her father-in-law was alive to support her. With her father-in-law, she gained knowledge about farms. She regularly visits to Regional Research Station Abhor to learn about fruit cultivation, new techniques and also get a variety of seeds. She also visited the Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana Kisan Mela, to learn about new techniques of farming. Right now, she is using drip irrigation to grow organic vegetables at her home. No doubt she felt alone after her husband's death, but other hand, she felt proud that she made decisions related to farming and became a successful farmer.

Case Study 3: Amandeep Dhillon: Farmer and Women Helper

Amandeep Dhillon was 60-year-old woman farmer staying in Abohar city. She was cultivating kinnow and cotton on a 73-acre of land. Earlier, she was a housewife and took care of her children. However, in 2005, her husband faced health issues and had difficulties in looking after his farming. So, it was a turning point in Amandeep's life that she needed to come out of her house and start farming activities. She had an M.A. in English but had no idea about farming. So, she learned farming techniques from her brother and took initial training from CIPHET for Kinnow cultivation. When she, started working in the field, she met many women workers who were working in the field. She got to know that women need a space in society, especially in the economic realm. It was a challenge for Amandeep to work in the field, so she made a group of 30 women and gave them employment in her field. She also tried to know about their socio-economic background so that she could give them economic aid during hard times. She opened a small household-based bank for women, where they can save their and also get money without interest during they need it. She also took the initiative to give employment to the village women on her farms. She made her farm women-friendly and secure for them. She encouraged housewives and unemployed young girls to work in her place. So that they can earn a livelihood. She said that though it was tough and also needed to put more effort, I wanted to do something for them. Amandeep mentioned that I am educated and have family support, but these women need someone who can support them. So, I came forward for them and started giving them employment on my farms. At least, they don't need to go outside of the village or face employment shortages. They are part of my family. Now, she has started a processing unit, where they sort the oranges according to

their size and sell them in the market. All work is done by the women, not by men. Even Amandeep is helping with children's education to health. She helped all women's children to get admission to the village government school and all the expenses were borne by her. Other than that, she is also giving them financial help for health treatment. She said in a male-dominated society, women have a very small place and most of the time they remain busy with the household chores. So, such women have no contribution to the outer world and the economy. So, I am trying to give them a place that is making them mobile and outer of their private realm. Amandeep said I read "Changi Kheti" and "Progress Farming" magazines of Punjab Agricultural University to keep myself up to date in farming. Even during the Kisan mela, I usually visit the University to learn about new techniques, seeds, fertilisers, and scientific discussions on farming. The most challenging task for her is to look after her family and farms. In the village, no doubt some people do not like my work; they said she is manipulating our women and giving them employment, which is not good. However, for me, making women aware of their rights and knowing about their potential is more important. To make women economically empowered, first, they need to be aware. Recently, Amandeep has also tried to make a self-group of women to generate employment opportunities by starting an initiative in traditional knitting.

Case Study 4. Dolly Setia: Housewife to Entrepreneur

Dolly Setia is a mother of 3 college-going children and lives in Abhor City. She is very fond of pickle making and usually during any family functions, she prefers homemade pickles. Once, she made a mixed vegetable pickle for her father-in-law's death ceremony and all the guests liked it. Later, they demanded pickles from her. Then, her children told her not to she started her own pickle business. However, she does not know where to start and where to go. First, she registered for the CIPHET skill development program and took three months of certified training from them. Later, she created a self-help group called Setia Pickles and registered it through MSME. However, the next challenge is about what kind of pickle she will make and where to sell it. In all this, her family remains a big supporter, her husband helped her and suggested making seasonal pickles. He said he would go to the market and sell to shops. So, Dolly called her village women and shared her ideas with them. Though it is a tough decision for them, Dolly is ready to give them good incentives according to their working hours. Her husband invested money in this work. He is a farmer and has some savings. From those savings, Dolly purchased the required machinery, including a cutter, chopper, and big utensils for pickle mixing. So, they purchased seasonal vegetables and started their unit. Dolly's family worked with her to make their unit more successful, and her sons started working with her. One son started taking care of all the financial matters, the second son was working with labour women, providing them pick and drop facility to their houses. Dolly's husband started working in the market unit and selling their products to the market, friends, and relatives. Her daughter started taking care of the media side, and she opened an online account on Instagram and posted videos for orders. She is a chef by profession and also promotes pickles at her university. Dolly participated with her team in various center and state Melas. She visited Delhi, Ludhiana, Chandigarh, Bathinda, Gurdaspur, and Patiala, etc. to sell their products. She mentioned that it is a joint effort of the family and her family supports her to start this business. Secondly, it is a way to

empower my village women by giving them work in their households. We always give priority to our workers, especially women, who need financial support and independent careers. So, it is a way forward for women's empowerment and helping each other.

Discussion

Women's Control over Economic Means

Indian society is based on patriarchal norms in which males hold a dominant position. This family system is also prevalent in Punjab. In a rural family setup, power and resources are majority controlled by males and they remain the decision-makers of the family. This family system is divided into public and private spheres, in which the public sphere usually remains under the control of males, while females are confined to the private sphere. In such a situation male is symbolised as the breadwinner of the family and the female is confined as the caretaker of the household. The power dynamics also favour the male and control all economic means of the family. In such situations, the woman has no control over family resources. However, women's participation in the public sphere and especially in the working areas may make changes in their lives. From the above case studies, it was found that women were making economic choices through working on farms and other activities. This findings of the study allined with the Kaur (2022) that women became part of the economic sphere as their participation increase in the public sphere.

In the case of Amandeep, she was a housewife and was taking care of her children. Her husband was the breadwinner of the household; however, sudden changes occurred due to an emergency and she became the owner of the household. She started working in the fields and taking care of the economic means of the household. She also realised that her husband is not narrow-minded and gave her a space to work in the economic realm. Now, she was controlling all the economic means of the family. However, after all the changes, she became aware that women must have participation in the economic realm and she motivated her village women to work with her. She also tried to make them economically independent and have control over their economic means. Similar to Renu Sangmar, she was not aware of the family affair; all things are taken care of by her husband and father-in-law. She was confined to household chores. However, after her husband's death, she started working as a full-time farmer, which was a challenging task for her. Because she did not have any knowledge about her family's economic system. After controlling the family business, she became the family earner and head of the household. She engaged village women to work with her and gave them a safe place of work and provided them an economic security.

Women and Role in Decision-Making

In the above topic, we already discussed that Punjabi society is based on family power dynamics, who have control over economic means, and that person hold the major share of power in decision-making. Power dynamics, in which the elder male or son usually holds the major share of decision-making power. However, in the case studies, women became the head of the household and started taking decisions for their households. It is a change in the family decision dynamic. The reason is that earlier, women were not part of the economic affairs and their role was confined to household chores. While their participation in the economic realm made them aware of their rights and their place in society. It boosts their confidence and

makes them family decision-makers. Similarly Kaur and Kaur (2022) mentioned that the control over economic means and decision making capacity lead women towards independent and head of the household. Moreover, women become rational and take decisions for the societal welfare.

It is not confined here only; they utilise their rational mind to make changes in the lives of other women. They tried to make decisions not only family arena but also for society. In the case of Indu, she started her processing unit after taking certified training for the CIPHET. She didn't confine such a role to her life; rather, she motivated other women to participate in her processing unit. She tried to give them free education and employment on her farm. So that they can make their decisions independently. She also tried to utilise her decision-making power for the welfare of society rather than being confined to her family. Similarly, in the case of Dolly Setia, she started a Self-help group and motivated women to take decisions about their lives. She tried to provide them with a space to earn their livelihood. Even motivate them to take decisions about their life in the public sphere. Amandeep Dhillon also mentioned

“In the village, no doubt some people do not like my work; they said she is manipulating our women and giving them employment, which is not good. However, for me, making women aware of their rights and knowing about their potential is more important”.

Women and Mobility

In the patriarchal family setup, the woman had a lack of control over family resources which caused less visibility in the public sphere. Most of the time, women of the household remained dependent upon their male counterparts to visit outside of their household, which caused less mobility outside of their household. However, control over economic resources and participation in the economic sphere made women visible outside of their households. It also made them more mobile in their household. They are participating in farming activities, selling their products in the market and also working in the male realm, which in itself is a change in their routine life. Participation in the public sphere, dealing with workers, going to training centres, visiting the market for selling and purchasing goods and going to banks, such minute changes had a bigger effect on women's lives. Polas and Afshar Jahanshahi (2021) mentioned that women become more mobile and self reliance after active participation in social entrepreneurial activities.

It is not confined to here only; they motivate other women to participate in economic activities, which increases women's mobility outside their household and makes them aware of the public sphere. As Dolly Setia mentioned, she participated in various Melas and visited Delhi also to sell their products. It boosts their confidence and participation in the outer world. Even Indu also mentioned that her participation in various training programs for “Organic Farming” and also winning various appreciation awards, certified her mobility outside the household. She gained visibility in society due to her work and mobility in the public sphere.

Women as Agents of Change

Women started their businesses to take care of their families, and due to a family emergency. However, it remained a turning point in their life. They became aware of their rights and space in public life and made changes in their overall life. As Amandeep Dhillon mentioned that

“ I am educated and have family support, but these women need

someone who can support them. So, I came forward for them and started giving them employment on my farms. At least, they don't need to go outside of the village or face employment shortages. They are part of my family. Now, she has started a processing unit, where they sort the oranges according to their size and sell them in the market. All work is done by the women, not by men. Even Amandeep is helping with children's education to health. She helped all women's children to get admission to the village government school and all the expenses were borne by her. Other than that, she is also giving them financial help for health treatment. She said in a male-dominated society, women have a very small place and most of the time they remain busy with the household chores. So, such women have no contribution to the outer world and the economy. So, I am trying to give them a place that is making them mobile and out of their private realm”.

Similarly, Indu discussed about making changes in women's lives. As she said

“Organic farming is an occupation that makes you closer to nature and also gives a positive outcome in life. Women are the major change-makers in society, even in history. So it is our responsibility to take care of our environment. For that, I am educating our village women by providing them with full-time employment in my organic farms. So that they learn about how to earn their livelihood and also preserve nature at all costs. We are the ones who can make changes in the environment and it is our responsibility to save the environment. So, I want to change the lives of village women and girls by providing them with education in organic farming so that they can become self-sufficient.

Renu Sangmar also helped her village women to come forward and increase their participation in farming activities. She time to time visited the Punjab Agricultural University and met many scientists to try to find occupational opportunities for women. She motivated them to participate in her farms and started giving them handsome incentives for their upliftment.

So these women started their occupation and led them towards the market. They tried to make their women workers self-reliant. They used their given opportunity to bring a positive change in their society. They used their potential to give a better life to other parts of society. They tried to create a chain reaction in their society and work as an agent of change in society by providing a space to their co-women partners. Agrawal et al. (2023) mentioned that the initiative of social entrepreneurial activities are not making women self-sufficient rather bring change in the society, family and also towards gender roles in the society.

Conclusion

The study revealed that women shifted their realm from the private to the public sphere, boosting their confidence and increasing participation in the decision-making process. It also increased women's mobility and economic well-being, which caused their presence in society. These women become more active and expressive in a patriarchal household setup.

These women also tried their best to give space to other women. They create a safe place for the village women and provide them with opportunities to participate in the economic realm. They break the social barrier and stigmas related to women's participation in the public sphere. These women didn't make changes in their lives, only rather made efforts for other women by providing them employment

opportunities. They also helped in the reduction of poverty in rural women by providing them with a safe place of work and near their homes. Participation in the public sphere and becoming a successful entrepreneur also breaks the gender barriers and social stigmas related to women. This growing participation in the economic sphere may also give them an advantage to bargain their power in household decision-making. In the past, women were mostly housewives who lacked confidence and access to economic prospects. However, there was a rise in household income and women's earnings in social entrepreneurial activities. As a result, males in the home began to see women's abilities and assist them in their economic endeavours. Such changes also changed the women's status in their households and made them family decision-makers. We have the best example of Dolly Setia, as her whole family was helping her in her social entrepreneurial activities. These women felt empowered and gained self-confidence in their social and economic realms.

From the study, it was found that most of the women used their self-learning skills and without much support. Even women face various challenges to increase their visibility in society and at the family level that need to be given consideration. From the study, it is visible that rural women, especially housewives, need adequate training and skill sets to get rid of economic poverty. There is a need to provide them with institutional mechanisms to train the poor in marketing and logistics, other than skill development. This study will help policymakers and NGOs to curb gender discrimination and poverty-related problems using entrepreneurial activities.

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